

NEGATIVE EUPHEMISMS IN THE MEDIA

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Abstract. *As the main sign of manipulation, researchers call the hidden nature of the impact, the very fact that should not be noticed by the object of manipulation. That is why, from the numerous linguistic means of manipulative influence, our attention was drawn to euphemisms - words or expressions that can veil facts and events that have a deliberately unfavorable system of assessments for the public consciousness and can cause antipathy. The linguistic nature of euphemisms is such that they distract the recipient's attention from the forbidden concept, as they are associated "in the minds of the participants in the speech act with denotatives outside the tabooed circle." The specificity of the use of euphemisms as a means of expressing a negative assessment in the texts of modern Russian print media is considered.*

Key words: *negative appraisal, euphemisms, mass media language.*

Introduction

Many modern researchers note a tendency towards coarsening, an increase in the level of aggressiveness of the language of the media. This is due to the proclamation of freedom of speech, the removal of ideological filters in the post-Soviet period. At the same time, the opposite phenomenon is also observed - the euphemization of the speech of modern Russian media, the active use of language units that serve to soften, veil, aestheticize negatively evaluated concepts.

«Euphemism is an indirect communicative strategy of ameliorative orientation, which involves the use of both linguistic and extralinguistic means (euphemisms) in order not to create a feeling of communicative discomfort in the interlocutor (that is, for the purpose of tabooing, politeness, aestheticization, softening, veiling, distorting information)» [1, p. 7]. The euphemization of media-political discourse is caused by the increased conflict potential of this sphere. The fact that communication is carried out in public and often touches upon potentially conflicting issues of the social and political life of society forces the speaker to be especially careful in choosing language means of expression, because «the more severe the social control of the speech situation and self-control by the speaker of his own speech, the more likely the appearance of euphemisms» [2, p. 34]. This is especially true for modern media, which are gradually adopting the experience of the Western culture of public communication associated with the phenomenon of political correctness. In addition, euphemisms are a powerful means of speech manipulation, which is extremely in demand in modern media and political discourse.

Evaluation is one of the specific features of media speech, due to the influencing nature of journalistic texts. A negative assessment in its various manifestations is very often found in the texts of modern media. At the same time, many authors, realizing the responsibility for their publicly expressed opinion, seek to avoid conflict situations, to be politically correct, therefore they try to express a negative assessment in a softened, veiled form. To express a negative assessment in a latent form, modern publicists resort to the use of euphemisms

Discussion

The negative-evaluative potential is due to the very nature of euphemism, because «euphemisms are emotionally neutral words or expressions used instead of synonymous words and expressions that seem obscene, rude or tactless to the speaker» [3, p. 318]. The designation of an undesirable denotation as the main feature of euphemism: «the denotation of a euphemism corresponds to an object or

phenomenon characterized by a negative assessment or a negative connotation» [4, p. 76]. Another essential feature of euphemism is a formal improvement in the nature of the denotation in comparison with the original nomination, smoothing out the negative connotation. The specificity of euphemisms lies in the fact that, while softening the negative expressiveness of the replaced nomination, they retain a semantic connection with it. Due to the veiled, but clearly perceived by native speakers of the negative semantics, an assessment is created. This assessment is much weaker than that of the original nomination, but it is clearly felt by native speakers, stronger or weaker depending on how understandable and semantically transparent the euphemism is.

The process of euphemization is directly related to the sphere of moral assessments. Euphemistic substitutions are made for those concepts that are considered immoral, antisocial in the system of values of a given society. Euphemization affects nominations that can evoke negative associations in the reader, on the basis of which a negative assessment can be created. For example, in modern society, violence, cruelty are considered inhumane, so in the texts of the press you can often find a euphemism special interrogation methods to refer to interrogation methods based on the use of physical violence, torture: However, the White House has repeatedly stated that it will not support a ban on the use of special interrogation methods. interrogation techniques.

Obviously, the use of euphemisms helps to reduce the aggressive orientation of the text, while maintaining a negative assessment, cf.: *Mariah Carey drives a jet ski drunk* (Express, 05/10/2009) and *Vladimir Presnyakov drank in the trash* (Yellow newspaper 05/24/2013). With the similarity of semantics, the euphemism *podshofe* is much softer, more correct than the colloquial expression *drunk in the trash* with a reduced emotional coloring.

Not all euphemisms are characterized by negative appraisal. Often, with the help of euphemisms, words are replaced that are inappropriate in a given communicative situation, that do not comply with the rules of speech etiquette: «We

hope that everything will work out and the Donetsk activist will survive. But, I'm afraid, the irreparable will happen - Gubarev is literally on the verge of life and death, they said from the Ukrainian capital (Tomorrow, 03/19/2014)»; Masha Sharapova in an interesting position? (Express, 10/24/2013). These euphemisms do not contain a negative assessment, but direct nominations of the described phenomena (the irreparable will die instead, the pregnant instead of in an interesting position) could sound tactless. «But in modern media, euphemisms are still more often used to create a negative assessment» [5, p. 22]. There are different ways of expressing a negative assessment with the help of euphemisms.

Meiosis is often used to create euphemisms. In such cases, the negative assessment is softened, because the euphemism indicates a lower intensity, incompleteness of the expression of a negative feature compared to the original nomination. This can be achieved using different language means. For example, the author can use periphrastic phrases with particles not at all, not at all, far not, definitely not, etc., adverbs of measure and degree, and other parts of speech with the meaning of incomplete expression of the sign: Obviously, the state of the city treasury is not at all rosy and, quite possibly, the lack of any optimism about the prospects for improving its position forced the prominent "United Russia", the mayor of Kamensk-Uralsky Mikhail Astakhov, to make a proposal far from social populism ... (Vedomosti, 05/21/2014); The Oryol region is definitely not the richest, but such children are treated there without interruption (Novaya Gazeta, 07/07/2014); After all, Gino, unlike the soccer pop star Beckham, is not at all handsome (Sports Day by Day, 06/22/2012); If it is introduced as a mandatory norm, in my opinion, this is not very true (Novaya Gazeta, 08/06/2013); This difference angered some of the singer's fans, because everyone knows that the star is already over fifty, and such a "rejuvenation" looks a little silly (Novaya Gazeta, 11/21/2014). Such turns sound less categorical (cf. ∴ definitely not the richest instead of the poor, not at all handsome instead of ugly, etc.).

A similar mechanism for creating euphemistic substitutions is often carried out with the help of derivational means. For example, verbs with a prefix indicate the incompleteness of the action, so they are often used as euphemisms: There are universities that have both 40 and 60 branches, which really, to put it mildly, trade in diplomas from the head university (Nezavisimaya Gazeta, 06/20/2014); In the village of Repino, they did not disdain to lie: Vishnevsky was reported on one institution in which none of the deputies work.

Very often in the media a method of euphemization is used «transfer from view to view» [6, p. 74], when an undesirable lexeme is replaced by a neutral synonym with a more general, vague meaning: In Kyiv, riots began again near the Russian embassy (Obshchaya gazeta, 05/22/2014); Tensions remain between Sudan and South Sudan... As a result of the bombing, several people were killed (Nezavisimaya Gazeta, 04/24/2012); The militants of the Right Sector went to clean up Donetsk (Rossiyskaya Gazeta, 05/27/2014); Armed with automatic and other small arms, about 30 people started shooting at the windows of the front doors, so they suddenly managed to break in and neutralize the guards who were there.

As such euphemistic substitutions on the pages of the media, book vocabulary is often used, including scientific terms: I don't know what constitution they read, but it seems to me that this is some kind of aberration of consciousness armed rebellion (Vzglyad, 02/24/2014) (aberration - delusion, deviation from the truth, from Latin *abberatio*); Liberalization of gas prices on the domestic market, by definition, will increase the profitability of gas production companies (Nezavisimaya Gazeta, 08.06.2010) (price liberalization - instead of raising prices); It is reported that the biggest gang of the city "Comando Vermelho" wanted to regain control of the slums, which she ceded because of the so-called operation to pacify poor areas (Soviet sport, 03/29/2014) (pacification - instead of reprisal, pacification by punitive measures, from Latin *pacificatio* – appeasement); Absolutely biased, absolutely politicized report (Vzglyad, 06/19/2014) (biased - instead of bought, untruthful; The State Duma warned PACE against destructive sanctions against the

delegation of the Russian Federation (Rossiyskaya Gazeta, 01.04.2014) («destructive - instead of destructive» [8, p. 49], «sanctions - instead of prohibition, punishment» [9, p. 707]); Kyiv wants to neutralize the “Right Sector” and the Maidan self-defense (Rossiyskaya Gazeta, 06/29/2014) («neutralize - instead of destroy» [10, p. 48]). Most of these lexemes are of foreign origin. Such substitutions perform well their function of veiling and mitigating negative expressiveness until they are fully assimilated by the language system and remain not fully understood by most addressees. In addition, as you know, nominations of foreign origin are subconsciously perceived by native speakers as more respectable, tactful.

One of the most common techniques for creating euphemistic substitutions is paraphrasing. The use of descriptive phrases makes it possible to hide the negative essence of the named phenomenon, to shift the focus in favor of its neutral or positive properties, which helps to level the negative assessment: Today, for the first time, Russia announced that the unipolar world has ended (Rossiyskaya Gazeta, 03/18/2014) («instead of US dikatate» [11, p. 22]); Society strives for one goal - to limit the influence of each other. There is a kind of consensus with the opposite sign (Nezavisimaya Gazeta, 04/08/2000); Managed democracy prescribed for accountants.

A similar mechanism for removing a negative assessment is implemented in euphemisms based on metaphorical transfer: the United States creates a security vacuum (Nezavisimaya Gazeta, 12/18/2001) («instead of terror and unrest» [12]). Encountering such euphemisms in texts, the reader usually does not have time to comprehend what phenomenon is behind the euphemistic substitution, since the excess of information in modern media political discourse makes it difficult to critically evaluate it.

In order to euphemize the text, precedent phenomena can be used: Savik Shuster once again justified his reputation as Judas (Express, 06/08/2014); Metropolitan Lady Macbeth - Beyond (Rossiyskaya Gazeta, 03/31/2011); If a friend turned up all of a sudden... What is happening in Ukraine has revealed not only the

true nature of the attitude towards Russia of "partners in the West", but also the real quality of "friendship" with us of the states of the post-Soviet space (Literaturnaya gazeta, 05/21/2014). In the absence of direct negative characteristics, the assessment in such cases is formed on the basis of associations associated in the mind of the bearer of culture with one or another precedent phenomenon.

Results

So, in most cases, euphemistic substitutions are successfully used by journalists to neutralize negative appraisal. At the same time, euphemisms tend to be assimilated by the language system and become journalistic cliches, which significantly reduces their ability to veil the negative essence of the named phenomena and, accordingly, soften the negative assessment: An authoritative entrepreneur legalized through his nephew.

Conclusion

So, euphemisms are actively used to express a negative assessment in modern media and political discourse. They successfully fulfill their function of mitigating negative appraisal, veiling the negative essence of the described phenomenon. This is due to the fact that the reader, encountering a euphemism in the text, cannot immediately recognize what is hidden behind the euphemistic replacement. As a rule, the reader either does not have sufficient knowledge to trace the mechanism of euphemistic substitution, or does not pay attention to the euphemism that merges with the general flow of information. «Therefore, it is natural that euphemisms can express a negative assessment more or less intensively, depending on how much their essence is clear to the reader» [7, p. 2175].

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